

aromatic rice cultivars. The cytoplasmic base has been diversified to protect future rice hybrids from outbreaks of disease or insect pests. Breeding indica / tropical japonica hybrids has begun with the development of CMS lines in the background of tropical japonica. ■

Developing Pusa 3A, a Basmati CMS line

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Basmati rice occupies a significant place in India's rice economy on account of its high export potential. With the release of Pusa Basmati 1, the first high-yielding semidwarf Basmati variety meeting quality standards, India leaped ahead in Basmati rice production. Further improvement in Basmati yield may be possible with the adoption of hybrid rice technology.

Various Basmati rice lines were testcrossed with IR58025A. Pusa Basmati 1 showed complete sterility and proved to be a perfect maintainer of wild abortive (WA) cytoplasmic sterility. The pollen sterility in the F_1 hybrid was 100%. The F_1 was backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1 and a BC_1 population of about 600 plants was raised. All the plants showed 100% pollen sterility. Segregation was observed for various plant characters. Twenty BC_1 plants that were closer to Pusa Basmati 1 for various characters were backcrossed to Pusa Basmati 1. About 30 seedlings in each of the 20 BC_2 progenies showed 100% pollen sterility. Cooking quality of the 20 pollen donors was analyzed. The best five donors showing good cooking quality were selected on the basis of their similarity to Pusa Basmati 1 for various agronomic characters such as plant height, panicle length, spikelet morphology, and days to 50% flowering. These plants were again backcrossed to the selected five pollen donors, thus maintaining the identity

of the pollen donors for the respective population. The BC_3 plants raised from the above crosses were screened for pollen sterility; all the plants were 100% sterile. Three plants were selected from each BC_3 progeny row and these were again backcrossed to their respective pollen parent from Pusa Basmati 1. Progenies from pollen plants No. 1 and 3 (Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3) had all the morphological characters of Pusa Basmati 1. They were further backcrossed to their respective pollen plants—Pusa Basmati 1-1 and Pusa Basmati 1-3, both with excellent cooking quality traits. The CMS line derived from Pusa Basmati 1-3 has been named Pusa 3A. This line shows stable sterility under different environmental conditions at New Delhi and Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, during the two different rice seasons. This line is now being used extensively for testcrossing with both Basmati and non-Basmati male parents. A few promising combinations with Basmati restorers have been identified. It was also found that heterosis with non-Basmati restorers was far greater than with Basmati restorers for various characters, including yield. ■

Screening rice genotypes for thermosensitive genic male sterility reaction

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Two-line rice hybrids were found to be more heterotic than three-line hybrids. Constraints of the three-line system can also be avoided in the two-line system. Any rice variety can be used as a pollen parent in the two-line system irrespective of the presence of a restorer gene. The two-line system also offers the advantage of easy seed production. For photoperiod-sensitive genic male sterility (PGMS) vs thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS), the TGMS system is more useful for the weather

conditions that prevail in southern India. We therefore screened some diverse genotypes to identify potential lines. Staggered sowings and plantings were done during the 1995-96 wet and dry seasons. We carried out pollen studies on these lines and also recorded spikelet fertility. Data on pollen sterility were correlated with minimum, maximum, and daily mean temperatures during the critical period of sensitivity of the lines, that is, 10 d from the third day after panicle initiation.

During the 1995 wet season, one TGMS line—IR68949-5-31-34—exhibited complete pollen and spikelet sterility for a period of 51 consecutive d. The mean daily temperatures during this 51-d period were between 27.1 and 28.4 °C. The same line transformed to partial fertility when the average temperatures reached 26 °C and below.

During the 1996 dry season, a second TGMS line, IR68945-33-4-14-40, was found to be completely sterile for a period of 15 d. The mean daily temperature regimes at the critical period of sensitivity ranged from 23.5 to 26.5 °C. Later, this line transformed to partial or complete fertility. The two TGMS lines identified in this study may be used to develop new two-line rice hybrids for enhancing heterosis and thus production and productivity of the rice crop. ■

Identifying parental lines in hybrid rice by RAPD fingerprinting

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The commercial production of hybrid rice hinges on three-line breeding, male sterile, maintainer, and restorer lines. Developing and producing new parental lines are essential for the sustainability of hybrid rice. Characterizing these lines based on morphological and phenological characters consumes time, lacks sufficient resolving power, and is influenced by

the environment. Therefore, we need to characterize parental lines, especially restorers, using biotechnological tools.

DNA was extracted from commonly used parental stocks (CMS lines IR58025A and IR62829A; their isonuclear maintainer (B) lines IR58025B and IR62829B; and elite restorer (R) lines IR40750, IR9761, IR34686, and IR10198. These extracted DNA samples were amplified by polymerase chain reaction using 20 arbitrary oligo-nucleotide primers. The amplified products were analyzed on agarose gel and scored for the presence or absence of bands. With selected primers (OPA-7, OPA-12, OPA-20, OPB-19, OPU-17, and OPW-4), sufficient polymorphism could be detected to allow identification of individual stocks. The isonuclear maintainer and the CMS lines were, however, indistinguishable. The randomly amplified polymorphic DNA (RAPD) analysis is a potentially simple, rapid, and reliable DNA finger-printing method for identifying parental stocks and determining the parentage of rice hybrids. As this molecular technique verifies the degree of dissimilarity between the parental lines, the RAPD analysis may also help in identifying new potential combinations based on genetic divergence. ■

Exploiting the in vitro ovary culture technique to breed rice hybrids

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The thermosensitive genic male sterility (TGMS) system has a high potential to develop two-line hybrids, which are more economical for seed production. The ovary culture technique can also help to improve or develop new lines for several economic traits. We therefore cultured unpollinated ovaries from plants of five crosses involving TGMS UPRI 95-140 (P1), the good

ideotype UPRI 95-117 (P2), and maintainers UPRI 95-139 (P3) and UPRI 95-130 (P4). Quality rices—Basmati 385 (P5), Haryana Basmati 1 (P6), and UPRI 95-145 (P7)—were also cultured. The cultured ovary from hybrid plants P1/P2 pretreated at 8 °C for 14 d on an N6 medium supplemented with 500 mg lactoprotein hydrolysate (LH) L⁻¹, 4 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹, 2 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1 mg BA L⁻¹ produced 0.5% calli. Regeneration of these calli on an MS medium containing 500 mg casein acid hydrolysate L⁻¹, 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1.5 mg BA L⁻¹ produced four clumps of completely green plantlets and one partially green plantlet. One of these green plantlets showed the TGMS trait. It was completely spikelet sterile during the panicle heading period between 15 Jun and 5 Sep, but was partially fertile and set seed after 18 Sep. Seed set was 0.5, 1.7, 4.8, 12.3, and 6.4% at heading on 18 Sep, 1 Oct, 12 Oct, 26 Oct, and 1 Nov 1995, respectively. The ovary culture-derived line was dwarf, with an intermediate plant type, and flag leaf and

panicle length similar to those of the female parent. But this line produced more spikelets.

The unpollinated ovaries of F₁ plants derived from maintainer/quality rices cultured on an N6 medium supplemented with 0.5 mg 2,4-D L⁻¹, 4 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 1.0 mg BA L⁻¹ produced calli. Callus induction was 3.33, 2.67, 1.33, and 2.00% for P5/P3, P3/P5, P6/P4, and P7/P4, respectively. But plantlets were regenerated only from P5/P3 (46.7%) and P3/P5 (50.0%) on an N6 regeneration medium supplemented with 500 mg LH L⁻¹, 0.5 mg NAA L⁻¹, and 2 mg kinetin L⁻¹. The performance of seven H1 clones of the former cross showed four clones with long, bold grain and a nontranslucent endosperm, whereas clones 6 and 7 had long, slender grains and a translucent endosperm free of an opaque area and were comparable in quality with Basmati 385. Exploitation of these lines to improve quality and yield potential in a hybrid rice breeding program is in progress. ■

Pest resistance — diseases

A variety with durable resistance to rice blast

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San-Huang-Zhan No. 2 (SHZ), a rice variety developed by the Guangdong Academy of Agricultural Sciences, was cultivated on 1,533 ha in 1986. It then spread from 8,000 ha in 1987 to 10,977 ha in 1995 and showed excellent resistance to blast in an environment favorable to blast in Guangdong, China. Therefore, we assumed that SHZ is a variety with durable resistance to blast.

Looking at the resistance performance of SHZ, we found that its resistance spectrum (RS) was more than 95% from 1985 to 1995 (Table 1). In 1995, the RS of SHZ was 99.5% under artificial inoculation with 220 isolates in Guangdong and 95.2% with 124

isolates of *Pyricularia grisea* from eight rice-growing zones in China. Furthermore, we screened a stable isolate (GD-V1) that is compatible to SHZ to investigate the reaction of SHZ compared with the reaction of the resistant check IR36 and the susceptible check B40. Entries were inoculated at the 5-leaf stage. Lesion density (LD) and lesion size (LS) were scored by the method of Roumen and diseased leaf area (DLA) was measured by the method of Notteghem. To make a better comparison, we converted the observed data (OD) of LD, LS, and DLA into relative value (RV) on the basis of B40, and computed the mean of LD, LS, and DLA. At the same time, resistance of the varieties was assessed in fields in eight rice-growing zones in China by the Standard of the National Blast Co-research Group. Results (Table 2) indicated that the resistance of SHZ and IR36 is different because SHZ